

THE ROLE OF MANAGERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW GENERATION OF ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT CONCEPTS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Tukhtaboev Abdurashid Tursunovich

Professor of the Department of "Accounting and Management". Andijan Machine-Building Institute. City of Andijan. Uzbekistan
earlarchil@yahoo.com

Annotation.

This article shows that one of the most important tasks of any company in the digital economy is to distinguish it from many competitors in the market, attract buyers and turn them into their regular customers. To this end, it was emphasized that the task of achieving accelerated development using the advantages of high technologies in industrial production is urgent, and the role of managers in this process is important.

Keywords.

digital economy, high-tech industry, management, innovation, management methodology, efficiency, roadmap.

In the current conditions of the digital economy, one of the most important tasks for any company is to distinguish among many competitors in the market, attract buyers and turn them into its regular customers. This is necessary to increase sales, increase profits and achieve high competitiveness. As you know, one of the main ways to solve this problem is the introduction of new production technologies and their management.

The fact that industrial production is rapidly developing with the predominance of high-tech industries is the embodiment of today. New production technologies are being developed and prospects are being determined. Advanced manufacturing technologies are understood as technologies and technological processes (including the equipment used) controlled by a computer or controlled by microelectronics and used in the production of goods and services.

In modern conditions of digitalization, industrial enterprises must reorganize their activities, including information systems, in connection with their current development. This is associated with serious risks, as the implementation of ready-made or custom-made projects often fails.

Existing methods and tools do not always allow to reduce risks and solve issues of reorganization of business processes of the enterprise at different stages. The methodology of building a complex system of enterprise activities is also of great importance.

Developing an effective approach to managing business processes and new technologies in an enterprise is not an easy task. To ensure the sustainable development of an industrial enterprise, the application of innovative management theories and methodologies is required. The processes taking place at the enterprise require constant attention of management, process owners and personnel ensuring the implementation of business processes.

In the process of improving and optimizing processes, it is necessary to maintain the level of efficiency and achievements achieved as a result of the implementation of the technological approach.

To implement the process of digital transformation of the enterprise, it is proposed to use the following algorithm:

1. Formation of a competent expert working group capable of diagnosing the organization's activities and current business processes;
2. Independent verification of the organization's activities and the formation of initial data on the level of digitization of the enterprise and production business processes, software components of the digital production used;
3. Assessment of the level of digitization (digital maturity) and the level of information security of the enterprise;
4. Identification of problems, identification of priorities for the introduction of digital technologies, risk assessment;
5. Analysis of existing or new concepts of digitization of the enterprise according to the selected priority;
6. Formation of a roadmap for the introduction of digital technologies;
7. Making decisions on the economic feasibility, efficiency of the use of digital technologies in the company's activities and achieving the current level at the level of the organization's management, approval of the implementation roadmap;
8. Implementation of the roadmap for the introduction of digital technologies;
9. Control and analysis of the results of implementation and key performance indicators of the company in order to make adjustments;
10. Work on scaling issues if there is a positive trend.

When forming a roadmap, it is necessary to take into account the level of material and technical potential and the need for its modernization, as well as the

level of the personnel potential of the enterprise and the need for professional development and the level of motivation of the organization's personnel.

The modern method of digital economy is characterized by the development of concepts of a new generation of enterprise management, among which we can single out the technologies that we use: artificial intelligence, robotics, drones, 3D printers, the Internet of Things, blockchain innovations and advanced capabilities, as well as virtual reality. The involvement of surrounding objects in the global Internet space has been called the "Internet of things" (Internet of things, IoT). Marketers say that the market of technologies related to this phenomenon has already reached significant volumes: according to a study conducted by the international company IDC, the costs of IOT solutions in the world amount to \$2 trillion per year, and by 2020 will exceed \$7 trillion. The Internet of Things is useful where there is a demand for speed, quality and price, that is, in the mass consumption industry, as well as in the industry as a whole.

The application of new concepts gives enterprises competitive advantages. Depending on the main functions of the technology, it can be divided into 3 groups:

- data entry (drones);
- data processing (artificial intelligence, blockchain);
- output data (robotics, 3D printers, augmented and virtual reality).

Depending on the chosen priority direction, when implementing the algorithm of the digital transformation process of an enterprise, it can be proposed to use the following modern enterprise management concepts: For example, the use of IT technologies changes the business processes of an organization and significantly increases operational efficiency by reducing the duration and duration of the production cycle; reducing operating costs and improving energy efficiency; reducing the number and duration of equipment downtime, increasing the level of its loading; improving the quality of products.

Blockchain is one of the newest technologies aimed at changing existing business models and processes in companies. It is not widely used yet, and the available use cases are limited to some examples. Although the first application of cryptocurrency-related technology has caused a resonant debate, the technology itself may have business applications unrelated to cryptocurrencies.

The use of blockchain technologies improves the work of an enterprise or organization in the field of financial transactions and transactions with tangible and intangible assets, and also changes the management system by tracking and registering completed transactions (external and internal).

The issue of using and implementing modern technological solutions in the activities of enterprises in the context of digital transformation remains important. According to the results obtained by scientists conducting research in this field, the answer to this question can be presented as follows: big data is already used in the activities of enterprises in the context of digital transformation, 34% of respondents use it, 21% plan to implement it; 28% use the Internet of Things, and 26% plan; 24% use robotics processes, 20% plan; augmented virtual reality-15% use, 26% plan; artificial intelligence-22% use, 20% plan; biometrics - 24% use, 14% plan; robots - 19% use and 21% plan implementation [9].

In conclusion, we can say that digital transformation poses a big and multidimensional task for leaders. Firstly, it is difficult to understand where the expectations of customers and technologies that are developing at a tremendous speed will go next. Secondly, it is necessary to radically and quickly restructure a large enterprise, possibly to stabilize the existing business so that it can compete with digital startups. Finally, leaders have an important role to play (in collaboration with others) in solving the complex task of maximizing the value of digitalization for both society and the industry.

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